

ELECTROCHEMICAL STUDY of SCHIFF BASE and WELDING PARAMETERS with RESPECT to CORROSION of METAL PARTS MANUFACTURED by WAAM-CMT in H₂SO₄ 0.5 M

Youcef BELLAL¹, Antar BOUHANK¹ and Linda TOUKAL²

¹Research Center in Industrial Technologies CRTI, P.O.Box 64, Cheraga 16014 Algiers, Algeria E-mail: y.bellal@crti.dz/youcefbellal324@yahoo.fr

²Ferhat Abbas University Setif-1, Faculty of Technology, Department of Engineering Process, Laboratory of Electrochemistry and Materials (LEM) Setif, Algeria

ABSTRACT: Metal parts have been manufactured using the WAAM-CMT additive manufacturing technique from ordinary steel wire. In order to know the influence of the welding parameters on the mechanical and morphological resistance of the latter, we have varied the current intensity and the traveling speed of the torch. These parts will be exposed to the following medium H₂SO₄ 0.5 M, for this end, a study of the impact of the inhibitor named L with respect to metal corrosion parts was carried out by Potentiodynamic Polarization and Impedance Spectroscopy (SIE) in H₂SO₄ 0.5 M in the absence and presence of different concentrations of the inhibitor and immersion temperature. A high inhibition power is observed: 69.45 % for L=10⁻⁴ M, 71% for L= 510⁻⁵ M at t=30 min and T=20°C. This inhibition is almost stable as a function of the temperature. The adsorption of inhibitor on the steel/solution contact surface is confirmed by SEM, EDS and Electronics Microscope. This organic compound is therefore promoters in the aggressive medium H₂SO₄ 0.5 M.

KEYWORDS: WAAM-CMT, Corrosion, Schiff Base, Potentiodynamic Polarization, SEM, EDS.

INTRODUCTION

Net-shape manufacturing by additive manufacturing (AM) has gained considerable momentum over the last decade and is emerging as a technology of the future. Laser and electron beam technologies have been commercially exploited to produce metal parts for commercial use. Unfortunately, existing metal-based AM technologies are limited due to high equipment sophistication, high equipment cost, low deposition rate, and property issues. These constraints ultimately hamper the overall development and growth of this wonderful technology. There is a need to develop new cost-effective technologies that have the potential to improve deposition rates, are less sophisticated in equipment and are reliable in practice. Wire arc additive manufacturing (WAAM) based on cold metal transfer (CMT) is a cost-effective and rapid method for prototyping high-quality metal parts digitally. Through continuous surfacing, this uses the arc as a heat source to fuse the wire. The software and hardware of WAAM system include Dingzhi PNT-3D trajectory simulation software, data communication lines, power supply, wire feeding system and execution

actuator. The manufacturing of metal parts mainly relies on the repeated positioning of displacement, speed and execution actuator, to realize the repeated reproduction of weld pool through point-by-point control on the line, surface and body. In addition, there are a number of factors directly affecting the dimensional accuracy of formed parts, such as the accuracy and stability of the execution actuator, key technological parameters, welding mode and stability of arc heat sources. According to the characteristics of the energy beam, the more stable the arc is, the more conducive it is to the control of the forming process, that is, the continuity of the formed morphology [1-2]. Therefore, cold metal transfer (CMT) technology evolved from gas inert gas and gas active gas welding, (MIG/MAG) has become the main heat source method for WAAM. It features very low heat input, splash-free droplet transition, stable arc, precision and accurate in material entry and other characteristics.

A number of variations of CMT technology are present including CMT technology, Pulsed CMT (CMT-P), Advanced CMT (CMT-Adv), Advanced Pulse Pattern CMT (CMT-PADV), etc. Compared to Selective Laser Melting (SLM), Direct Metal Deposition (DMD) and Electron Beam Fusion

Deposition (EBFM). CMT technology has the following advantages: low equipment cost, high arc deposition rate, high precision forming, and easily popularize the welding process to a large extent, solving the precision requirements of forming. In this regard, a large number of researchers have shown interest and a lot of researches on process parameters and models have been done, resulting in rapid development of equipment technology [3-4]. The metal parts manufactured by the CMT technique generally have somewhat complex structures whose surface treatment cannot intervene, on the other hand, the latter will be used in aggressive places such as H₂SO₄, HCl, NaCl, etc. which requires a mandatory coating: chemical (paint (organic/inorganic), Zn Molten) or electrochemical by transition metals (Zn, Ni, Cr, Cu, Au etc.) on the surface of the additively manufactured metal parts to give corrosion resistance with a homogeneous and pleasant morphology. Schiff bases are widely used in recent times in several fields (biology, civil engineering etc.) due to their corrosion inhibiting efficiencies [5-7].

The Arc-wire additive manufacturing process by CMT "WAAM-CMT", (Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing - Cold Metal Transfer) developed by the company FRONIUS, allows a versatility of function among others cold welding such as the reduction of heat input. This technique has been adopted by many industries because of the significant savings generated by reducing downtime and production costs. This project is carried out in a series of tasks leading to the control, monitoring and therefore the modelling of any subsequent operation. The different additive manufacturing processes using metal wires differ mainly by the heat source used.

We can distinguish several processes using the filler metal in this form: Laser and wire additive manufacturing (WLAM) [8] or wire-fed laser (WFLB) [9]. Electron beam free-form manufacturing (EBF3) [10]. Wire arc additive manufacturing (WAAM): the heat source used here is an electric arc. This process is based on the combination of a welding generator and a movement system to manufacture components.

Unlike the two previous processes, the use of an enclosure to control the atmosphere is not mandatory. A flow of inert gas near the weld pool is sufficient. The main applications of processes based on metal wires are structural components and relatively large dimensions (greater than one meter). The main fields of application are naval, aerospace and aeronautics [11].

The objective of this work is to propose a methodology for manufacturing parts using WAAM/CMT technology from ordinary steel wire.

Trajectory generation is a decisive step in the additive manufacturing process. Therefore, we will seek to implement methods to address these limitations. The generation of trajectories is based on manufacturing parameters (layer thickness, feed rate and process parameters, etc.) whose selection process has been poorly explained (new domain). To this end, we will seek to propose a method for choosing the operating parameters adapted to the implementation of the process. The deposition of the metal during manufacturing is accompanied by a modification of its internal structure which can affect its material health.

We will therefore seek to evaluate, quantify and explain the mechanical performances of the printed parts through morphological analyses (SEM, EDS, Metallography, etc.) but also to extract the electrochemical parameters (polarization resistance and inhibition rates).

EXPERIMENTAL

This part is devoted to the presentation of the results of the electrochemical study by cyclic voltammetry and impedancemetry (EIS) of the inhibitory efficiency of the synthesized Schiff base against the corrosion of ordinary steel manufactured by CMT, as well as the results of the surface morphology study carried out by SEM/EDS and optical microscope.

The choice of the deposition current intensity and the torch scanning speed that influences the mechanical and morphological characteristics of the parts manufactured by CMT and knowing the adequate and real conditions for the manufacture of a more resistant metal part with a homogeneous and pleasant exterior surface. Moreover, the addition of products (organic / inorganic) as a corrosion inhibitor in low quantity for the protection of parts manufactured by CMT.

For this, we printed walls ($x=10$, $z=6$ cm) in ordinary steel by CMT at different welding parameters such as: torch deposition speeds ($V= 800$, 1200 and 1600 mm/min), current intensity ($I= 25$, 50 , 75 and 100 A) while maintaining Q Argon/CO₂= constant = 12 L/min whose Argon/CO₂ volume percentage is (97.5/2.5), the incrementation $Inc= 0.5$ mm on the Z axis. Then, we used an original Schiff base named L with a molar mass $M=374.38$ g/mol and chemical formula C₂₀H₁₄O₄N₄ synthesized and characterized at Electrochemistry and Materials (LEM) Laboratory, Engineering Process Department, Faculty of Technology, Ferhat Abbas University Setif-1, Setif, Algeria. Afterwards, we studied the inhibitory power at different concentrations of L against the corrosion of ordinary steel in H₂SO₄ (0.5 M) using potentiometric

polarization and impedancemetry (EIS). The temperature parameter is added to distinguish the stability of the L layer deposited on the surface of the steel/aggressive solution contact. Finally, surface morphology analyses by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) coupled with EDS and optical microscope were completed to confirm the inhibitory action of L.

Parts Printing by CMT

First, we printed ordinary steel walls using the CMT technique, which we used to vary the current intensity and the torch scanning speed. We noticed that the walls manufactured at the intensity $I = 25, 50$ A have a fine and discontinuous morphological appearance, thus, the more the current intensity I increases, the thicker the wall is (figure 1). On the other hand, we observed at the intensity $I = 100$ A the collapse of the wall and the appearance of molten bubbles, which led us to focus the research work on steels manufactured only at $I = 75, 100$ A, favouring the results of steels manufactured at $I = 75$ A for their well-finished morphological appearances.

Fig. 1 Printing of ordinary steel walls by CMT at ($I=25, 50, 75$ and 100 A) and ($V= 800, 1200$ and 1600 mm/min).

ELECTROCHEMICAL MEASUREMENTS

General recommendations

Electrochemical measurements were performed using a three-electrode cell: 1/ Working electrode (WE): Ordinary steel manufactured by CMT coated with an inert resin whose surface had previously undergone mechanical polishing using abrasive papers with different grain sizes (360-2000) and cleaned with bi-distilled water, degreased with acetone and finally dried at room temperature before immersing them in different solutions, 2/ Auxiliary electrode (AE): A platinum plate ($S=10\text{mm}^2$), 3/ Reference electrode (RE): ($\text{Hg} / \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2 / \text{KCl}$). The

experiments were performed in a thermostated cell. Electrochemical impedance (EIS) measurements and potentiodynamic polarization curves were recorded using a Potentiostat "CH Instruments, Electrochemical Workstation". The whole thing is connected to a microcomputer equipped with software appropriate to the said device.

In our study, the working electrodes were steel bars type: ER70S-6 of 1 cm^2 surface with the following chemical composition: % by weight: $\text{C}=0.09$; $\text{P}=0.012$; $\text{Si}=0.95$; $\text{Mn}=1.65$; $\text{S}=0.018$; $\text{Cu}=0.35$.

Before starting and recording the polarization curves, the open circuit potential (OCP) is maintained for 30 minutes until a steady state is reached. EIS measurements were performed at the open circuit potential (OCP) in the frequency range from 100 kHz to 10 mHz with 10 points per decade and a scan rate $v=1\text{mV/s}$ in the interval -700 to -300 mV. The current-potential curves are obtained in potentiodynamic mode.

After recording the cathodic branch, the open circuit potential was re-established before determining the anodic branch. The exploitation and plotting of Tafel curves were used to determine the different electrochemical parameters (corrosion potential (E_{corr}), corrosion current density (i_{corr}). The electrochemical parameters of the constant phase element (CPE) and the polarization resistance (R_p) in the presence and absence of inhibitor at $T=293-323 \text{ K}$ in H_2SO_4 0.5 M are calculated by Z view Software. Then the inhibition efficiency EI (%) is given by the relation:

$$EI(\%) = \frac{i_{\text{corr}} - i_{\text{corr}(\text{inh})}}{i_{\text{corr}}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$EI(\%) = \frac{R_p(\text{inh}) - R_p}{R_p(\text{inh})} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where:

➤ i_{corr} and $i_{\text{corr}(\text{inh})}$ are the corrosion current density values without and with inhibitors, respectively, relative to the corrosion potential and determined at the intersection of the two Tafel lines anodic and cathodic slopes of the Tafel lines.

➤ R_p and $R_p(\text{inh})$ are the charge transfer resistance (polarization) values without and with inhibitors, respectively.

The impedance diagrams are given in the Nyquist representation. The polarization resistance (R_p) and the double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) were obtained from the Nyquist plots using the semicircle fit.

Electrochemical study of the corrosion inhibitory power of ER70S-6 Steel

The inhibitory efficiency of L and the corrosion inhibition mechanism were examined by potentiodynamic polarization and by impedancemetry as a function of: the concentration of L and the immersion temperature after a time $t=30$ min.

2. 1/ Potentiodynamic Measurements

a/ Effect of Concentration of L Current Intensity and Torch Speed

Tafel corrosion curves of ER70S-6 steel in H_2SO_4 solution 0.5 M in the absence and presence of L at various concentrations are shown in Figure 2. According to the shape of these curves, it can be said that the addition of the Schiff base results in a decrease in the current densities (i_{corr}) for all steels at different printing parameters (current intensity and torch speed) and a shift in the corrosion potentials (E_{corr}) towards more positive values for an immersion time and temperature (t_{imm}) = 30 min and $T = 20^\circ C$. These results confirm the inhibitory action of L.

Fig. 2 Tafel curves for corrosion of ER70S-6 steel in H_2SO_4 0.5 M in the absence and presence of different L concentrations, current intensity and torch speed.

b/ Temperature Effect

Tafel curves of ER70S-6 steel immersed in H_2SO_4 solution 0.5 M in the absence and presence of L at the optimum concentration (10^{-4} M) were plotted

in the temperature range 293-323K (Figure 3). It is observed that as the temperature increases from $20^\circ C$ to $50^\circ C$, the corrosion potential values shift from -493.0 mV/Hg/Hg₂Cl₂/KCl to -461.8 mV/Hg/Hg₂Cl₂/KCl (Figure 3). This shift confirms the inhibitory action of L even at high temperature. The inhibition rates are almost consistent of the order of 70 % with the increase in temperature. This shows the stability of the adsorbed layer on the steel surface up to $T=50^\circ C$.

Fig. 3 Tafel curves for corrosion of ER70S-6 steel in H_2SO_4 0.5 M in the absence and presence of L 10⁻⁴ M at different temperatures.

2. 2/ Impedancemetric Measurements

As we have previously and briefly demonstrated with the potentiodynamic technique, the presence of L positively affects the electrochemical behavior of steel immersed in H_2SO_4 0.5 M. In order to confirm these results, the EIS method was used to explain the steel/solution interface behavior.

Equivalent circuit

In order to establish a model for the steel/solution interface in the presence and absence of the inhibitor, the obtained EIS data were fitted to the equivalent electrical circuit shown in Figure 4 [5]. The impedance spectra of sample show a single capacitive loop, which indicates that the corrosion of carbon steel is controlled by charge transfer process [12–15]. The circuit consists of the electrolytic resistance R_s , the charge transfer resistance R_{ct} and the constant phase element CPE. The latter replaces the double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) in order to give a more accurate fit to the experimental results. It is recommended to use the CPE to model the frequency dispersion generally related to surface heterogeneity [6].

Fig. 4 Electrochemical equivalent circuit used for simulation of the impedance spectra.

a/ Current Intensity and Torch Speed Effect

Effect of current intensity and torch speed on the electrochemical behavior of ordinary steel immersed in H₂SO₄ 0.5 M solution is shown in Figure 5. It is observed that the impedance has been significantly affected. The Nyquist plots obtained are semi-circular and their diameters increase with increasing torch speed and the larger diameters are obtained at the highest current intensity (I=100 A).

Fig. 5 Nyquist diagrams for ordinary steel walls made by CMT at different deposition rates and current intensity in H₂SO₄ 0.5 M, T=20 °C.

Fig. 6 Bode (a) and phase angle (b) plots for ordinary steel walls made by CMT at current intensity I= 50 , 100 (A) and deposition rate v=1600 mm/min in H₂SO₄ 0.5 M, T=20 °C.

Table 1. Impedancemetric parameters of ordinary steel walls made by CMT at different deposition speed, current intensity and L concentration in H₂SO₄ 0.5 M, T=20 °C.

Current Intensity I (A)	Speed V (mm/min)	Medium	Rs (Ohm/cm ²)	Rp (Ohm/cm ²)	CPE * 10 ²	EI (%)
100	800	H ₂ SO ₄	4.492	76.16	16.69	
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 5 10 ⁻⁶ M	4.159	110.3	12.38	30.95
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁵ M	4.103	151.8	9.77	49.83
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 5 10 ⁻⁵ M	3.974	330.1	5.48	76.93
	1200	H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁴ M	3.997	318.5	5.87	76.09
		H ₂ SO ₄	4.122	56.16	22.98	
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 5 10 ⁻⁶ M	3.322	76.76	18.77	26.83
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁵ M	4.422	117.4	15.04	52.16
	1600	H ₂ SO ₄ + L 5 10 ⁻⁵ M	4.545	256.5	7.27	78.10
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁴ M	3.992	250.6	8.32	77.59
		H ₂ SO ₄	5.155	151	14.07	
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 5 10 ⁻⁶ M	4.97	294.4	7.51	48.71
75	800	H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁵ M	4.776	351.6	8.0	57.05
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 5 10 ⁻⁵ M	4.849	380.9	10.04	60.35
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁴ M	5.017	240.7	6.83	37.27
		H ₂ SO ₄	3.434	42.26	22.59	
	1200	H ₂ SO ₄ + L 5 10 ⁻⁶ M	2.695	54.56	24.99	22.54
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁵ M	3.261	82.06	20.95	48.50
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 5 10 ⁻⁵ M	2.623	108.3	16.80	60.98
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁴ M	3.666	273.4	7.483	84.54
	1600	H ₂ SO ₄	3.264	39.36	28.95	
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 5 10 ⁻⁶ M	3.183	62.88	20.83	37.40
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁵ M	4.624	104.3	11.38	62.26
		H ₂ SO ₄ + L 5 10 ⁻⁵ M	3.378	173	8.52	77.24
100	H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁴ M	4.767	173.5	9.67	77.31	
	H ₂ SO ₄	4.725	66.76	16.18		
	H ₂ SO ₄ + L 5 10 ⁻⁶ M	4.121	120	11.00	44.37	
	H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁵ M	3.913	94.53	5.97	29.37	
75	H ₂ SO ₄ + L 5 10 ⁻⁵ M	5.228	230.3	0.65	71.01	
	H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁴ M	4.228	218.5	0.67	69.45	

b/ Effect of L Concentration, Current Intensity and Torch Speed

The addition of the inhibitor leads to an increase in the R_p values contrary to the results given for steels without inhibitor. However, the R_p values tend to increase with increasing inhibitor concentration and the opposite is just for the double layer capacity (CPE) (Table 1, Figures 6, 7). This could possibly be explained by the massive coverage of L on the steel/solution contact surface.

Fig. 7 Nyquist diagrams for ordinary steel fabricated by CMT at different deposition speed, current intensity and L concentration in H₂SO₄ 0.5 M, T=20 °C.

c/ Temperature Effect

As the best printing speed and inhibition rate are obtained at I=75 A, v=1600 mm/min and C_L=10⁻⁴ M, we have chosen to plot the polarization curves at different immersion temperatures T=20, 30, 40 and 50 °C, where we have noticed that heat has an inverse influence on the polarization resistances, i.e. it reduces the mechanical resistances of the steels (Figure 8, Table 2).

Fig. 8 Nyquist diagrams for ordinary steel manufactured by CMT at I=75 A, V=1600 mm/min in H₂SO₄ 0.5 M with and without L=10⁻⁴ M at different immersion temperatures T=20, 30, 40 and 50 °C.

Table 2. Parameters obtained by impedancemetry of ordinary steel manufactured by CMT at I=75 A, V= 1600 mm/min in H₂SO₄ 0.5 M with and without L=10⁻⁴ M at different immersion temperatures T= 20, 30, 40 and 50 °C.

Medium	T (°C)	R _s (Ohm/cm ²)	R _p (Ohm/cm ²)	CPE * 10 ⁵	IE (%)
H ₂ SO ₄	20	4.725	66.76	16.18	69.45
H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁴ M		4.238	218.5	6.71	
H ₂ SO ₄	30	4.914	37.11	16.74	75.77
H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁴ M		3.096	153.2	5.49	
H ₂ SO ₄	40	3.784	21.26	13.45	73.63
H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁴ M		4.442	80.64	11.07	
H ₂ SO ₄	50	3.60	20.66	27.29	65.60
H ₂ SO ₄ + L 10 ⁻⁴ M		4.792	60.06	12.73	

3/ Morphological Study

3. 1/ SEM Analysis

The morphology of steel surfaces with and without L inhibitor immersed in an aggressive solution H₂SO₄ 0.5 M was studied by SEM technique. Crevice corrosion damage on the surface was observed for steel immersed in a solution without inhibitor, as clearly shown in Figure 8 a. On the other hand, the SEM image of steel surface immersed in a solution containing inhibitor L appears to be less porous and smoother Figure 9 b. These micrographs clearly show the presence of a product deposited on the steel surface. The latter are due to the adsorption of inhibitor molecule on the steel surface leading to corrosion inhibition [16, 17]. This result is in good agreement with the electrochemical study.

Fig. 9 SEM image of ordinary steel manufactured by CMT at I=75 A and V=1600 mm/min: (a) H₂SO₄ 0.5M, (b) H₂SO₄ 0.5 M + L 10⁻⁴ M, after an immersion time t=30 min.

3. 2/ EDS Analysis

EDS analysis of steel surfaces (Figure 10) without and with L immersed in an aggressive solution H₂SO₄ 0.5 M showed the following:

➤ The increase in the percentage of carbon, oxygen and the appearance of nitrogen element on the surface of steel immersed in H₂SO₄ 0.5 M + L 10⁻⁴ M (Figure 10 B) compared to that exposed to an environment of H₂SO₄ 0.5 M alone (Figure 10 A). This explains the presence of an organic product on the steel surface.

➤ The high percentage of iron (54.98% Fe) on the steel surface exposed to H₂SO₄ 0.5 M alone (Figure 22 A) in contrast to what was found in the presence of L 10⁻⁴ M (28.21% Fe) (Figure 10 B) confirms the continuous dissolution of the iron element from the steel core towards the steel/solution interface (Equations 3-7).

Furthermore:

The inhibition of corrosion is therefore due to the adsorption of this activated complex via the active sites of the inhibitors L. These results confirm the formation of a protective layer composed of activated complex [Fen(SO₄)_p(L)_m] which is responsible for blocking the access of SO₄²⁻ ions to the steel/solution interface.

Fig. 10 EDS spectrum of ordinary steel surface fabricated by CMT at I=75 A and V=1600 mm/min, (A): steel + H₂SO₄ 0.5 M, (B): steel + H₂SO₄ 0.5 M + L 10⁻⁴ M.

3. 3/ Optical Microscope Analysis

A dominant red-brown color corresponding to the rust was observed on the surface of steel free of inhibitor immersed in 0.5M H₂SO₄ with small traces of grey color suitable for the surface of the steel (see Figure 11-c). On the other hand, we have observed a dominant grey color on the surface of steel with inhibitor, which confirms the protection of the latter against corrosion in sulphuric environment 0.5 M (Figure 11-b).

Fig. 11 Optical micrographs of ordinary steel manufactured by CMT at I=75 A and V=1200 mm/min, (a) Bare steel (without H₂SO₄), (b) H₂SO₄ 0.5 M + L 10⁻⁴ M, (c) H₂SO₄ 0.5 M, after an immersion time t= 10 seconds.

CONCLUSION

From all the results obtained in this manuscript, it emerges that:

➤ The speed of the torch influences positively and proportionally on the mechanical resistance of the metal parts manufactured by CMT.

➤ The current intensity is a very sensitive parameter that must be varied carefully and the best current intensity to have a well-instructed metal wall is I=75 A.

➤ The studied Schiff base is an effective anodic inhibitor against the corrosion of ordinary steel manufactured by CMT in sulphuric medium 0.5 M.

➤ The protective action of L compound is significant even at high temperatures.

➤ The results found by all the methods used corroborate the adsorption of the complex on the contact surface steel/H₂SO₄.

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